

Voices Unveiled: Quality of Experience in Collaborative VR via AssemblyAI and NASA-TLX Analysis

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Abstract—In order to understand the sentiments between users as they worked together as part of a collaborative Virtual Reality (VR) task, this research analyzed voice interaction using Assembly AI. The real-time conversations between 11 pairs of users were captured as they performed a joint puzzle task. The users were in separate physical spaces but connected in a shared virtual setting. The extracted voice sentiments were correlated with self-reported frustration levels and task completion times. The findings reveal a significant positive correlation between negative sentiments and frustration ($r=0.73$, $p\leq 0.05$) and a negative correlation between positive sentiments and task completion time ($r=-0.87$, $p\leq 0.001$). This shows the relationship between sentiment (positive and negative) and task completion in collaborative VR. These results highlight the potential benefits of analyzing voice sentiment in collaborative VR applications.

Keywords—Quality of Experience (QoE), Virtual Reality (VR), Head-mounted display (HMD), Sentiment Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Collaborative or Social Virtual Reality (VR) is rapidly advancing how people collaborate on design tasks [1]. Within VR, participants' voice tones and speech patterns serve as a rich source of data for sentiment analysis, offering new insights into the group's emotional dynamics. This capability can add to the understanding of group Quality of Experience (QoE) [2]. Based on this concept, this paper outlines the methods employed to capture and analyze voice sentiments and investigates their relationship with user-reported frustration and performance metrics within immersive VR. By investigating these correlations, this study seeks to advance the field of human-computer interaction, aiming to improve our understanding of how emotional dynamics shape interactions within virtual collaborative settings.

Understanding QoE in collaborative VR design tasks is vital to user satisfaction, engagement, and performance [3]. Traditionally, user experience evaluation in VR has relied on subjective approaches such as user feedback, surveys [4] and questionnaires [5]. While these methods provide valuable insights into user's perceived experiences, they are inherently limited by their subjective nature. To counter these limitations, research has increasingly incorporated objective measures like physiological signals and interaction metrics [6], which include monitoring heart rate, and electrodermal activity, using haptic feedback, and employing machine learning algorithms to predict user engagement and satisfaction in immersive environments [6], [7], [8]. While

these sensors have been extensively used to measure QoE, conversational speech analysis has been rarely employed.

Speech is a primary mode of human expression and connection and holds a pivotal role in collaborative tasks [10], [11], [12]. With its capacity to convey emotional states, the human voice offers a unique avenue for enhancing communication and collaboration in VR [13],[14]. Studies have demonstrated the efficacy of speech analytics in extracting sentiments from conversations, which can help predict team performance [15] and quality of experience (QoE) [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21]. Sentiment analysis can effectively capture emotions in recorded voice conversations [22],[23] for quality evaluations.

However, recording voice in immersive VR is challenging, especially in environments where users interact via head-mounted display (HMD) [9]. The difficulty lies in capturing the voice in a setting where physical expression is obscured [10],[11]. Additionally, potential network issues in remote VR [12] collaboration can complicate the issue further. Even with data capturing challenges in such settings, successfully collecting and analyzing voice data can offer profound insights into the group Quality of Experience (QoE) and its invaluable contribution to the field.

Bridging these technical challenges, the current study has developed methodologies to mitigate the complexities of voice data collection and analysis. Recognizing the need to adapt to the constraints of VR environments, the research integrates advanced computational techniques and network optimization strategies to ensure robust and accurate sentiment analysis. This study employs a unique approach to collect voice in collaborative VR and then perform sentiment analysis of the recorded voice. Further, it explores relationship between sentiments, subjective metrics, and performance metrics.

By recording voice in an immersive environment where two users participate from separate physical locations wearing a Head-mounted display (HMD) to complete a puzzle task and subsequently reporting their experience in NASA-TLX [13]. This study aims to provide critical insights into user performance and satisfaction based on voice sentiments. These findings could inform more effective VR design strategies that boost group collaboration efficiency and alleviate user frustration.

II. RELATED WORK

QoE is the "measure of the delight or annoyance of the user's experience with the service or application"[14]. QoE evaluation for VR becomes particularly complex within a collaborative context due to its immersive, interactive, and multi-user capabilities [15]. The assessment of QoE in VR has been based on subjective methods, such as surveys and questionnaires, to gather users' perceived experiences [4], [5]. While these tools are invaluable for capturing subjective insights, they are inherently limited by their dependence on users' ability to retrospectively evaluate their experiences and the potential for bias they introduce. QoE researchers have started to explore objective measures like physiological signals [16] and eye-tracking data [17] to get a better understanding of QoE [6], [7]. However, these approaches provide direct, real-time data on individual users' emotional and cognitive states, with less emphasis on capturing the complexities of interactions and experiences in the multi-user VR environment.

Sentiment refers to a thought, opinion, or idea based on a feeling about a situation. Sentiment analysis aims to extract subjective information such as opinions, attitudes and emotions from human language. However, sentiment analysis was previously restricted to textual data [15]. The primary benefit of speech and audio data over textual data is the presence of emotions. Sentiment analysis stands out as an effective tool for evaluating QoE [18], [19], [20] in scenarios involving multiple users. Although sentiment analysis using voice data is not new, its application within QoE of VR settings, especially in active, collaborative environments, remains largely unexplored.

Previous studies have explored the use of voice communication to assess QoE. For instance, [18] focused on a multimodal physiological assessment of text-to-speech systems. [19] analyzed a QoE-based speech quality evaluation model to explore the performance of this model within multimedia applications, emphasizing real-time speech quality evaluation. QoE determination using EEG [20] and synthesized speech [21] has also been studied. [22] introduce a novel QoE model and method for audio broadcast over IP networks. These studies collectively demonstrate the diverse approaches to measuring and improving the QoE in various audio communication systems. However, extracting sentiments from speech for QoE assessment in VR represents a relatively new and promising direction.

Studies [23] [24] highlight the significant impact of perceived frustration on QoE during collaborative tasks like telemeetings. While one research study [25] proposes voice analysis within VR to study stress, its application in highly interactive VR settings is mainly unexplored. Our study bridges this gap by employing voice sentiment analysis in collaborative VR tasks, enabling extraction and analysis of sentiments in voice conversation and mapping perceived subjective experiences to it.

Our study stands out from previous ones by incorporating voice sentiment analysis into the assessment of QoE in collaborative virtual reality (VR), as shown in Fig 1. By

combining this innovative approach with established subjective and objective measures, we offer a comprehensive view of the emotional dynamics that come into play in collaborative VR settings. Our findings deepen the understanding of how emotional states impact user satisfaction and performance in immersive environments. This opens avenues for developing emotionally intelligent VR applications and systems, which marks a significant stride in the field. The entire architecture of our experiment is shown in Fig 1. The figure shows the virtual environment of the two participants with accompanied experimenters and their initial and final view of the collaborative session.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Participants and Teams

The study was performed with 22 participants across 11 teams of two each, ages 25 to 57 (median: 27.5, average: 29.4). Gender was evenly split: 50% female, 50% male. Ethnicity: 65% European/White, 20% Middle Eastern, 15% Asian. Backgrounds: 55% in computer science, 35% in electronics, and 10% in arts. Experience with VR: 15% never used, 65% used once, 20% experienced—technological proficiency: 15% low, 30% medium, 55% high.

1) *HTC Vive with handheld controllers*: Two handheld controllers and HTC Vive Pro Eye [17] were used for each participant to experience the VR application and facilitate collaboration. The two participants were in our university's lab rooms during the experiment. For the collaborative task, they joined the same virtual environment to complete a task, one being the leader and another being the follower, as shown in Fig 1. Each participant was represented by virtual avatars.

2) *Immersive VR Multiplayer Application*: Each participant worked with identical Windows 10 Pro 64 Bit Edition HP desktops with Intel(R) Core (TM) i7 - 9700K CPU @ 3.60GHz Processor fitted with NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 graphics card. Each desktop is connected to an HTC Vive Pro Eye with hand controllers. Both desktops had the Unity (2019.3.2f.1) VR application [26] and XR Toolkit [27] installed. Task roles were randomly assigned to the participants. Task completion time, with head and hand position data, was also recorded using the application. The Photon Unity Networking (PUN) [26], [28] SDK provided multi-user connectivity in VR through the University Network.

3) *Audacity Application for Recording Sound Conversation in VR*: Audacity [29] is a widely used open-source audio editing and recording software compatible with Windows, Mac OSX, and Linux. It was used to record the voice conversation between two participants with the start and end times. (version 2.4.2) running in the background of the remote recorder's PC to record the call's audio. Audio files were saved in Audacity as uncompressed 16bit waves. Objective performance metrics collected on this equipment and applications are task completion time, pupil dilation, and voice conversation of participants.

4) *AssemblyAI for Sentiment Analysis*: AssemblyAI [30] provides accurate speech-to-text voice data for sentiment analysis and speaker detection. AssemblyAI handles

transcription and summarisation with POST and GET HTTP requests. First, the mp3 file from Audacity is uploaded with a POST request from which a URL is returned. This URL is then used in a second POST request, transcribing and summarising the uploaded file. This request is customizable via the data parameter passed in. After that, we get sentiments using NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit) and Python.

B. Laboratory Environment

Two participants were in two different rooms, and two experimenters supported and monitored them when they wore the HMD for the entire experiment. The physical rooms were exactly of similar dimensions. The experimenters monitored participants during the experiment so they did not get hit by the physical walls. The virtual environment looked very similar to physical rooms (see Fig. 1). We created avatars with blue-headed figures and animated fingers to enhance immersion and participant engagement and ensure natural interactive movements. This embodiment in VR fostered a sense of presence and realism, crucial for an authentic, collaborative experience.

C. Collaborative VR Task procedure

The task required participants to collaborate to move ten shapes, in a specific order, from the follower's room to the leader's room. The leader would solve a puzzle using the received blocks in the leader's room. Participants were randomly paired with one partner as a leader and another as a follower. The follower's objective was to follow the leader's instructions and provide the requested blocks to the leader. The leader had to describe the colour and shape of the blocks accurately. Both participants were confined to their virtual rooms and could not move beyond those boundaries. To transfer objects between rooms, the follower could pass them through a virtual window, as illustrated in Fig 1. The participants interacted with the virtual environment using HTC Vive Pro Eye head-mounted displays (HMDs) and hand controllers, which allowed them to manipulate virtual objects using specific buttons or controls.

D. Data Collection Order

At the beginning of the session, all participants completed the consent forms. The HMD was fitted, and participants

Fig. 1. Architecture of the virtual reality (VR) environment, wherein an experimenter in separate physical rooms accompanies each participant. The participants engage in collaborative tasks, while their interactions are recorded. The recorded voice data is then uploaded to the Assembly AI server for voice conversion. Subsequently, the converted voice data is transformed into text, enabling sentiment analysis.

were allowed to familiarise themselves with the applications and controls (as part of a training phase in a bespoke training environment). Audacity was running in the background along with the Unity Application to record the voice conversation. Then, participants progressed to the shared virtual environment and worked together on the shared task. After completion, the HMD was collected from the participants. The participants were given a NASA-TLX questionnaire to fill in the details regarding their experiences.

IV. DATA PROCESSING

Team performance was measured by task completion time. We collected each pair's audio conversations during the collaborative VR task. We also noted the number of hand controller clicks and the VR task's start and end times. After completing the VR task, they had to report their experiences through the NASA-TLX Questionnaire. The following section describes how the data was extracted and processed when the participants performed the task in the collaborative session and recorded their voice communication.

A. Recorded Conversation Speech Audio Data using AssemblyAI Interface

The participant-voice interaction was a crucial element in solving the task. We extracted sentiments and subjectivity from the real-time conversations to uncover potential correlations with performance, particularly within low-performing teams. By operationalizing effects from VR conversations and employing sentiment analysis techniques, this research seeks to unlock the capacity to predict group performance based on their emotions.

1) *Audacity For Recording*: The participants were recorded while working on the puzzle pick and place task with their assigned partner for data collection. The audio system used for the study was the inbuilt-bidirectional paired microphones in the HMDs. The conversation in VR was facilitated by the Photon Voice Plugin connected to the Unity VR application. One of the significant steps we took was extensive research on the tools to record audio data and store it in files. Audacity was chosen over Unity Recorder. Unity recorder had some limitations regarding space, poor crackling audio, and slowed down substantially after concurrent recordings. On the other hand, Audacity is free, open-source software with an easy learning curve, a multi-track audio editor, and a recorder for Windows.

2) *Comprehensive Noise Reduction Strategy for High-Quality Audio Data*:

To ensure the highest quality of audio data in our study, we implemented a structured four-tiered noise reduction strategy. First and foremost, we conducted experiments within soundproofed rooms, proactively minimizing external sound interference. Second, we employed HTC Vive Pro recorders with bidirectional paired microphones, noise cancellation features, and extended battery life, capturing apparent audio while reducing ambient noise. The third level involved the utilization of Photon Voice SDK's voice detection threshold, which filters recorded sound, transmitting it only when a predefined signal level threshold is exceeded. This feature effectively pauses voice

transmission during periods of silence and resumes when speaking resumes, preventing the transmission of unnecessary noise and conserving network resources. Finally, as the fourth level, the Audacity software was applied to post-process recorded audio data, further diminishing background noise and enhancing the dataset's suitability for comprehensive academic analysis. This multi-tiered noise reduction approach ensured the acquisition of pristine audio data, safeguarding the integrity of scholarly research.

3) *AssemblyAI for Voice Analysis*:

AssemblyAI API [30] converts automatic speech recognition (ASR) services, which convert recorded spoken language into written text. It is open-sourced. AssemblyAI's ASR technology is built on deep learning and neural network models. AssemblyAI API with Python was used to convert audio to text and then analyze it. The AssemblyAI then extracted speech utterances from only the team members and stored the speech data related to each ID in the AssemblyAI cloud. This process generated 11 datasets, each containing the transcription of the speech of two individuals in the collaborative task sessions. The sampling frequency used was 44100Hz. The ASR services convert recorded spoken language into written text and analyze the transcript's sentiment, recognizing each speaker's voice in the conversation. After converting speech to text, it goes into preprocessing (see Fig 1).

a) *Preprocessing*: The preprocessing involves six subprocesses, which are as follows:

- Tokenization. Vectors are tokenized using a customized regular expression to clean the text and remove unnecessary characters [31].
- Lemmatization (switching any word to its base root form) [32]
- Stemming [33] (reducing words to their word stems)
- Part of Speech (POS) is a technique that assigns each word in a document a specific grammatical category or label [34].
- Named Entity Recognition (NER) extracts information from text [35]
- Stop words Removal [36].

b) *AI model for classification*: AssemblyAI has built LeMUR (Leveraging Large Language Models to Understand Recognized Speech), a framework for processing audio files.

c) *Sentiment Analysis*: Sentiments are classified into three classes: 'Negative,' 'Neutral,' and 'Positive,' with values ranging from 0 to 1. Sentiment scores for all vectors in each dataset are measured. The sentiment values for each team are shown in Table 1. The overall conversation data process is schematically illustrated in Fig 1. Then, using the Python NLTK library and AssemblyAI, we determine each speaker's speaking time and the total percentage of positive, negative, and neutral sentiments.

B. Task Performance Metrics

Task metrics include the number of clicks by each participant to complete the puzzle task and the total time needed to complete the puzzle task. Clicks were recorded

using the OpenXR plugin and XRTK (Extended Reality Toolkit) input mapping in each participant's Unity application through HTC Vive hand controllers. We have combined the total number of clicks and represented them in Table 1.

C. NASA-TLX Questionnaire Result

The NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) is a widely used questionnaire employing a 20-point visual scale to assess mental workload across various domains. It consists of six subscales that measure cognitive, physical, and temporal demands, along with frustration, performance concerns, and overall effort required for task completion. The psychological and physical demands subscales measure intellectual/perceptual and physical work, while the temporal demand assesses time pressure. The effort component measures the mental and physical work required to achieve specific proficiency. Frustration evaluates the stress associated with task completion, and the performance component measures satisfaction with the completed task. In this context, focus was solely on the frustration component of the NASA-TLX, using it as a targeted metric to assess the level of stress experienced by participants during the evaluated tasks. We have taken each team's mean frustration score as shown in Table I

V. RESULTS

This study aimed to explore the relationship between different variables in VR collaborative tasks and identify key factors contributing to improve QoE. It focused on analyzing the correlations between voice sentiment, and other performance metrics. Data were gathered from 11 participants, capturing voice sentiments, the frequency of hand clicks, subjective frustration levels based on the NASA Task Load Index (NASATLX), and the total time taken to

TABLE I. VOICE SENTIMENT PERCENTAGE WISE (NEUTRAL, POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE), HAND CLICKS, NASA-TLX FRUSTRATION SCORE AND TIME TO COMPLETE THE TASK

Team No	Voice Sentiments			Hand	NASA TLX	Time
	Neutral	Positive	Negative	Clicks	Score	Time to complete
1	89.83	1.69	8.47	91	14	19:39
2	89.18	2.7	8.1	132	22	33:28
3	79.2	12.98	7.79	69	10	08:12
4	74.19	14.5	11.29	86	54	10:28
6	85.43	6.79	7.76	43	14	22:11
7	74.57	15.25	10.16	67	10	12:19
8	83.01	10.37	6.6	25	4	11:46
9	75.82	17.58	6.59	68	6	06:24
10	75.89	17.52	6.59	54	10	06:32
11	15.53	15.53	6.31	86	4	10:37

complete the VR task. Table 1 depicts all the data gathered from the participants.

The descriptive statistics for the collected data are as follows: The mean neutral voice sentiment score was 74.25 with a standard deviation (SD) of 17.59, the positive sentiment averaged 11.78 (SD = 5.14), and the negative sentiment averaged 7.93 (SD = 1.88). Hand clicks had a mean value of 73 (SD = 35.07), and the frustration level, as reported on the NASATLX scale, had a mean of 14 (SD = 12.52). The mean time for task completion was approximately 15 minutes (SD = 9.38 minutes), indicating variability in the efficiency of task completion across participants.

The graphical analysis consisted of a matrix of histograms and scatter plots, as shown in Fig.2. Histograms on the diagonal of the matrix provided the distribution of each variable. The negative sentiment histogram skewed towards lower values, indicating that most participants exhibited lower levels of negative sentiment during the VR task. Positive sentiment also showed a skewed distribution with a clustering of lower scores. The histogram for hand clicks suggests a wide distribution, reflecting variability in the interaction patterns of participants with the VR environment. A right-skewed distribution reflects frustration levels, while the completion time was left-skewed, suggesting that most participants completed the task in less time than the average.

Pearson correlation coefficients [37] were computed to assess the relationships between the variables. A statistically significant positive correlation was found between Negative Sentiment and Frustration ($r=0.73$, $p \leq 0.05$), suggesting that participants with higher negative sentiment tended to report higher frustration levels. Additionally, frustration levels had a significant negative correlation between Positive Sentiment and Completion Time ($r=-0.87$, $p \leq 0.001$), indicating that participants with higher positive sentiment were likely to complete the task more quickly. Statistically significant relations were shown with the red "*" mark in Fig 2.

Fig. 2. Matrix Correlation Plot showing scatter plot, histograms of each component and statistically significant correlations highlighting p-value with "*"***

While the correlation between Negative Sentiment and Positive Sentiment was negative ($r=-0.44$), and the correlation between Frustration and Clicks was positive ($r=0.41$), neither reached statistical significance. The relationship between Clicks and Completion Time ($r=0.57$) was positive, yet it did not achieve statistical significance within this study's sample size.

The significant correlations emphasize the impact of users' emotional states on their perceived workload and task performance in VR environments. These key findings, particularly the considerable correlations between voice sentiment, frustration, and task completion time, provide valuable insights into the factors influencing QoE in VR collaborative tasks.

VI. DISCUSSION

The study examines user QoE in a virtual reality (VR) collaborative puzzle task. It has offered novel insights into the interplay between their sentiments, expressed frustration, and performance metrics. Participants, situated in separate rooms and interacting via head-mounted displays (HMDs), relied solely on VR-mediated communication to complete the puzzle pic and place task. The real-time conversations between the two participants were analyzed using Assembly AI, which served as an interface for sentiment extraction.

The pronounced positive correlation between negative sentiment and self-reported frustration ($r=0.73$, $p\leq 0.05$) reinforces the notion that user dialogue, as a conduit of emotional state, can have a tangible impact on QoE. This finding corroborates research suggesting that negative emotions can impair collaborative efforts by increasing cognitive load and stress [38], [39]. The immersive nature of VR and isolation from physical cues due to the users being in different rooms might amplify this effect. The heightened emotional contagion in VR could mean that one user's negative sentiment can escalate the other user's frustration levels, thus affecting the collaborative dynamic.

Conversely, the highly significant negative correlation between positive sentiment and task completion time ($r=-0.87$, $p\leq 0.001$) highlights a critical aspect of collaborative VR tasks. Positive feelings, potentially reflective of effective communication and mutual encouragement, seem to facilitate better performance, aligning with findings that positive affect promotes cooperative behaviour and problem-solving skills [40], [41]. The result suggests that fostering a positive communicative atmosphere could be essential to efficient task completion in VR settings.

It is interesting to note the non-significant correlations involving the number of hand clicks. Clicking in VR is multidimensional, potentially signifying engagement, exploration, or confusion. Without the physical presence of a collaborator, users might rely more heavily on verbal communication, rendering hand clicks a less significant indicator of frustration or completion time in this VR context.

Assembly AI as a sentiment analysis tool introduces an additional layer to understanding user interaction. By leveraging real-time conversational sentiments, we can begin

to predict and possibly mitigate negative experiences as they occur. This capability could be particularly beneficial in remote collaboration scenarios, where non-verbal cues are not as readily perceived.

The absence of a significant correlation between negative and positive sentiments could be attributed to the complexity of human emotions, where users can experience a spectrum of feelings that are not strictly opposite. The use of sentiment analysis tools in VR may need to account for this emotional complexity to better cater to the nuances of user experience. Similarly, the absence of statistical significance in the correlation between hand clicks and frustration levels, despite the observed correlation, can be attributed to the interplay of factors such as the relatively small sample size, measurement sensitivity, and individual differences in user behaviour. While there may be a connection between hand clicks and frustration, the statistical analysis may not have had sufficient power to detect it conclusively. Moreover, the complex nature of QoE evaluations in VR, influenced by various sensory inputs and the multifaceted nature of user interactions, could have obscured the direct influence of hand clicks on frustration levels.

Further research with larger sample sizes and refined measurement methods may yield a more comprehensive understanding of this relationship. Future research should consider the implications of these findings for the design of VR collaboration platforms. Strategies to enhance positive sentiments, such as gamification or the inclusion of mood-boosting virtual elements, could be explored. Moreover, understanding the nuances behind the nonsignificant metrics, like hand clicks, could lead to a more refined understanding of user interactions and how they contribute to the overall QoE.

This study highlights the importance of a multimodal approach to QoE evaluations in collaborative VR by capturing sentiments from voice conversations in remote VR interactive collaborations and mapping them with objective and subjective metrics. This research suggests that sentiment analysis could be a powerful tool for enhancing QoE. The ability to dynamically adjust to users' emotions and flow may pave the way for more sophisticated, adaptive VR environments that cater to users' psychological and task-related needs in real-time.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study adopted a multimodal approach to evaluate users' QoE using voice conversation sentiment analysis, objective click metrics, user self-reports of frustration and task completion time. Assembly AI was used for sentiment analysis to extract sentiments from recorded conversations between users in separate physical spaces connected through a Unity VR Photon application.

It highlights a significant positive correlation between task completion times and positive sentiments, as well as a strong negative correlation between reported frustration and negative sentiments. These findings advocate for the

integration of sentiment analysis to enhance the accuracy and depth of QoE assessments in virtual environments.

Overall, this study highlights the importance of user sentiments in remote VR collaboration and the potential for AI-driven tools to provide deeper insights into user experiences. Integrating sentiment analysis tools like Assembly AI into VR applications promises a new era of user-centred, responsive virtual environments, fundamentally transforming how we interact and collaborate in virtual spaces.

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